

Research Article

The Impact of Enlightenment on Religious Faith

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Abstract

The Enlightenment was a purely European intellectual movement that took place in 17th & 18th centuries. The period of Enlightenment was also known as the Age of Reason. The central ideas of this movement were reason, humanity, nature, and God (religion). Reasoning was applied to religion and eventually Deism was formed and consequently Scepticism, atheism, and materialism were born. The French Revolution was influenced by Enlightenment thinkers. In the 17th century the philosophy of religion was completed influenced by Rene Descartes in France and John Locke in England. Descartes' Rationalism and John Locke's Empiricism led to the development of a more reasonable approach to religion. They appealed to the universal Religion of Nature or Natural Religion. The ending of the Enlightenment has been viewed as the foundation of the West's modern political and intellectual culture, bringing democratic values and the creation of liberal democracies. The Enlightenment affected religion by taking away magical, mythical, and mysterious aspects. In some cases it also created anti-church radicalism and the idea of the separation of church and state. The two important concepts that the enlightenment pushed over religion were 1. Reason over superstition 2. Science over blind faith.

Keywords: Deism, Scepticism, Atheism, Materialism, Rationalism and Empiricism.

Enlightenment

The Enlightenment, also known as the Age of Reason, was an intellectual movement and cultural ambience that developed in Western Europe during the 17th century and reached its height in the 18th century. The common element was trust in universal and uniform human reason as adequate to solve the cultural problems and establish the essential norms in life, together with the belief the application of such reason was rapidly dissipating the darkness of superstition, prejudice and barbarity. It was freeing humanity from its earlier reliance on more authority and unexamined tradition, and had opened the prospect of progress toward a life in this world of universal peace and happiness. The primary belief was that "man can understand the universe through his reason". So, it is the power of the reason, but not the power of the supernatural being that helps man to make his life. The goals of rational humanity were considered to be knowledge, freedom, and happiness.

Enlightenment has its origin in the scientific revolution of the 16th and 17th centuries. Among the leaders of this revolution in England were Francis Bacon (1561-1626), John Locke (1632-1704) William Godwin (1756-1836). In France from René Descartes (1596-1650) through Voltaire (1694- 1778) to Diderot other editors of the great twenty- volume Encyclopedie (1751-

1772). In Germany from Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz (1646-1776) to the critical philosophy of Immanuel Kant (1724- 1804).

Immanuel Kant defines “enlightenment” in his essays entitled ‘An Answer to the Question: What is Enlightenment?’ (1784), as “humankind’s release from its self-incurred immaturity; “immaturity is the inability to use one’s own understanding without the guidance of another.” Kant identifies enlightenment with the process of undertaking to think for oneself, to employ and rely on one’s own intellectual capacities in determining what to believe and how to act. Enlightenment thinking encouraged rational scientific inquiry, humanitarian tolerance , and the idea of universal human rights. Enlightenment philosophers from across the geographical and temporal spectrum tend to have a great deal of confidence in humanity’s intellectual powers, both to achieve systematic knowledge of nature and to serve as an authoritative guide in practical life. This confidence is generally paired with suspicion or hostility toward other forms or carriers of authority (such as tradition, superstition, prejudice, myth and miracles), insofar as these are seen to compete with the authority of one’s own reason and experience.

Enlightenment philosophy tends to stand in tension with established religion, insofar as the release from self-incurred immaturity in this age, daring to think for oneself, awakening one’s intellectual powers, generally requires opposing the role of established religion in directing thought and action. The faith of the Enlightenment is of becoming progressively self-directed in thought and action through the awakening of one’s intellectual powers, leads ultimately to a better, more fulfilled human existence.

Because of the scientific revolution there evolved many ideas against the blind faith in god and religion.

Scepticism:

It enjoys a remarkably strong place in Enlightenment philosophy. The philosophy of scepticism is exemplified prominently in Descartes’ Meditations on First Philosophy (1641), in which Descartes employs radical sceptical doubt to attack prejudices derived from learning and from sense experience and to search out principles known with certainty which may serve as a secure foundation for a new system of knowledge. However, scepticism is not merely a methodological tool in the hands of Enlightenment thinkers. The sceptical cast of mind is one prominent manifestation of the Enlightenment spirit. Another important figure is the Scottish philosopher David Hume. His concept of scepticism was developed in Book One of A Treatise of Human Nature (1739–40) and in his later Enquiries Concerning Human Understanding (1748). He says our idea of cause is based on nothing more than previous experience of one phenomenon being followed by another; all we know is a succession of events either in the sensible world or in our minds. To infer the operation of laws of cause and effect from observed sequences or clusters of events or ideas, even to infer the existence of a rational personality from groups and sequences of impressions and ideas in the individual mind, is quite illogical. Thus Hume brought to light the sceptical implications in the whole mainstream of European philosophical thought. If for Hume most things that people believe cannot be demonstrated by reason, this does not mean that we must rest in complete confusion and uncertainty. Pure reason, as he argued in A Treatise of Human Nature, is applicable only to investigation of the relations between ideas as in pure logic and pure mathematics. Such an investigation, Hume believed, could lead to a sound and fruitful science of human and general nature grounded on psychological fact. He developed his views on man, on ethics, on epistemology and kindred subjects in two volumes of essays An Enquiry Concerning Human Understanding(1748) and An Enquiry Concerning The

Principles of Morals (1751) . He finds that what is morally good is simply what is esteemed . There is an optimism underlying Humean scepticism for he believed that sympathy was an innate human characteristics and that it accounted in large measure of for the origin of morality. Much of Hume's arguments about morality was an apparent agreement with ideas popular in his age. The whole basis of his philosophical operations was radically counter to the mainstream of eighteenth century thought. His sharpest attack on the beliefs of his age was in Dialogues Concerning Natural Religion published posthumously in 1779.

Empiricism:

The rise of empiricism, both in the practice of science and in the theory of knowledge, is characteristic of the period. The belief in observation and experience as the basis of knowledge ,rather than logical deduction is called empiricism. Empiricism is an epistemological view of which holds that true knowledge or justification comes only or primarily form sensory experience and empirical evidence . it is one of the several competing views with in epistemology along with rationalism and scepticism.

If the founder of the rationalist strain of the Enlightenment is Descartes, then the founder of the empiricist strain is Francis Bacon (1561–1626). Though Bacon's work belongs to the Renaissance, the revolution he undertook to effect in the sciences inspires and influences Enlightenment thinkers. The Enlightenment, as the age in which experimental natural science matures and comes into its own, admires Bacon as "the father of experimental philosophy." Bacon's revolution (in *Novam Organum* 1620) involves conceiving the new science as (1) founded on empirical observation and experimentation; (2) arrived at through the method of induction; and (3) as ultimately aiming at, and as confirmed by, enhanced practical capacities (hence the Baconian motto, "knowledge is power").

Though the great seventeenth century rationalist metaphysical systems of Descartes, Spinoza and Leibniz exert tremendous influence on philosophy in the Enlightenment, the *Encyclopedia of Diderot and D'Alembert* is dedicated to three empiricists (Francis Bacon, John Locke and Isaac Newton), signals the ascendancy of empiricism in the period.

John Locke's *Essay Concerning Human Understanding* (1690) is another foundational text of the Enlightenment. Locke finds the source of all our ideas, the ideas out of which human knowledge is constructed, in the senses and argues influentially against the rationalists' doctrine of innate ideas. Locke's sensationalism exerts great influence in the French Enlightenment.

Locke's empiricism led other english philosophers in other direction. George Berkeley (1685-1753), Bishop of Cloyne, pushed lcoke's views to thier logical extreme and maintained in his *Treatise Concerning the Principles of Human Knowledge* (1710) that sensation cannot be taken as evidence of an objectively existing material reality which caused them ; the external world exists only insofar as it perceived by the individuals, and the only cause of individual perceptions can be the divine mind, though Berkeley' philosophy was not well received.

Deism, an unorthodox religious attitude that can be found in the writings of Edward Herbert in the first half of the 17th century. Belief that the universe was ordered , both physically and morally , by benign and sagacious planner was at the bottom of much eighteenth century deism: the great deistic argument from design. God becomes a distant if benevolent First Cause, morality consists in following those impulses to virtue which god implanted in man.

Deism refers to what can be called natural religion, the acceptance of a certain body of religious knowledge that is inborn in every person or that can be acquired by the use of reason and the rejection of religious knowledge when it is acquired through either revelation or the teaching of any church. Deism has been succinctly described as “religion without revelation”.

In Lord Herbert’s treatises five religious ideas were recognized as God-given and innate in the mind of man from the beginning of time:

1. The belief in a supreme being,
2. In the need for his worship,
3. In the pursuit of a pious and virtuous life as the most desirable form of worship,
4. In the need of repentance for sins,
5. In rewards and punishments in the next world.

These fundamental religious beliefs, According to Herbert , had been the possession of the first man, and they were basic to all the worthy positive institutionalized religions of later times.

In England at the turn of the 17th century this general religious attitude assumed a more militant form, particularly in the works of Toland, Shaftesbury, Tindal, Woolston, and Collins.

Commenting on deism Hudson says “ good sense became the idol of the time. Good sense meant a love of the reasonable and the useful and hatred of the extravagant, the mythical and the visionary...the deists who are the advocates of purely natural religion, kept up a persistent attack upon revelation and the miraculous... the assumption was the supremacy of logic and reason”.

Though the Deists differed among themselves and there is no single work that can be designated as the quintessential expression of Deism, they joined in attacking both the existing orthodox church establishment and the wild manifestations of the dissenters.

So, Deists expressed a belief in a God who was the architect of nature’s wonders, a God who had set the world in motion and formulated the laws by which it operated. They believed in the existence of a system of rewards and punishments in the next world administered by that God. They also believed in the obligation of people to lead virtuous and pious lives.

Atheism

Atheism is, in general, the critique and denial of metaphysical beliefs in God or spiritual beings. As such, it is usually distinguished from theism, which affirms the reality of the divine and often seeks to demonstrate its existence. Atheism is also distinguished from agnosticism, which leaves open the question whether there is a god or not, professing to find the questions unanswered or unanswerable.

Atheism, however, casts a wider net and rejects all belief in “spiritual beings,” and to the extent that belief in spiritual beings is definitive of what it means for a system to be religious, atheism rejects religion.

Materialism

Materialism, in philosophy, is the view that all facts (including facts about the human mind and will and the course of human history) are causally dependent upon physical processes, or even reducible to them.

The word materialism has been used in modern times to refer to a family of metaphysical theories (i.e., theories of the nature of reality) that can best be defined by saying that a theory tends to be called materialist if it is felt sufficiently to resemble a paradigmatic theory that will here be called mechanical materialism. This article covers the various types of materialism and the ways by which they are distinguished and traces the history of mater.

Materialism languished throughout the medieval period, but the Epicurean tradition was revived in the first half of the 17th century in the atomistic materialism of the French Roman Catholic philosopher Pierre Gassendi. In putting forward his system as a hypothesis to explain the facts of experience, Gassendi showed that he understood the method characteristic of modern science, and he may well have helped to pave the way for corpuscular hypotheses in physics. Gassendi was not thoroughgoing in his materialism in as much as he accepted on faith the Christian doctrine that people have immortal souls. His contemporary, the English philosopher Thomas Hobbes, also propounded an atomistic materialism and was a pioneer in trying to work out a mechanistic and physiological psychology.

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